

School Canteen Best Practices and Innovations that Deliver Quality Service, And Support Income and Its Operation

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the extent of the implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service, sustaining income, and ensuring efficient operations at Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School during School Year 2023–2024. Grounded on the standards set by DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2017 and DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2007, the study assessed the canteen practices and innovations such as compliance to food safety standards, daily operations and financial management, 7s embedded canteen, data-based inventory system, VOC-based system, reward and incentive system, recognition system, canteen gift certificate, loyalty and discount cards, satellite canteen system, and Project Online Canteen Report System (OCRS). Using a descriptive research design, data were gathered from 400 respondents consisting of 300 students, 70 teachers, and 30 parents who were selected through purposive sampling. A researcher-made questionnaire checklist was used, consisting of a five-point Likert scale to determine the extent to which best practices and innovations were implemented. The composite results revealed that the school canteen's best practices and innovations were implemented to a very high extent, as reflected by the overall mean of 4.84 ("Very Much Practice"). Key areas such as compliance with food safety standards, data-based inventory system, reward and incentive system, and satellite canteen system obtained the highest ratings, indicating strong adherence to quality service and efficient operations. Likewise, daily operations, financial management, and the implementation of the 7S embedded canteen and Project OCRS further demonstrate effective and organized management practices. However, systems such as the VOC-based system, recognition system, and loyalty programs received slightly lower ratings, interpreted as "Much Practice," suggesting areas for further enhancement. The study concluded that the Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen has successfully institutionalized best practices and innovations, resulting in high-quality service and sustainable income and operations. Several recommendations were proposed to further enhance the effectiveness of the best practices and innovations implemented in the Baras Pinugay Integrated High School (BPIHS) canteen. These include continuous monitoring and strengthening of compliance with DepEd Orders, as well as the regular assessment of innovations to ensure their effectiveness and sustainability. It is also recommended that canteen staff undergo regular training on food safety and customer service to maintain high service standards. Furthermore, customer feedback mechanisms such as surveys and suggestion boxes should be strengthened to better address the needs and concerns of stakeholders.

Introduction

School canteens play a vital role in promoting the health and well-being of learners by providing safe, nutritious, and affordable meals. At the same time, they serve as an important source of income that helps support various school programs, projects, and operational needs, contributing to the overall sustainability of the school. According to the World Health Organization (2021), healthy school food environments contribute to improved nutrition and better learning outcomes among students.

In the Philippine educational system, school canteens are recognized as essential support mechanisms in fostering learner development and sustaining school-based initiatives. Nonetheless, ensuring quality service and maintaining operational sustainability remain major challenges, particularly in public schools where financial resources, management systems, and technical expertise are often limited.

To address these concerns, the operation of school canteens is guided by legal mandates and policy frameworks issued by the Department of Education. DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2007 emphasizes that school canteens must provide nutritious food at affordable prices while generating reasonable income to support school programs. Likewise, DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2017 mandates strict compliance with food safety and nutrition standards to ensure the protection and promotion of learners' health. In addition, Republic Act No. 11037, or the Masustansyang Pagkain para sa Batang Pilipino Act, reinforces the government's commitment to addressing malnutrition and promoting healthy eating habits among Filipino children through sustainable feeding and nutrition programs. These policies highlight the vital role of school canteens in advancing both educational and health-related goals.

In support of these policies, studies have shown that effective management practices significantly influence canteen performance. Edianon (2024) found that effective school canteen management is associated with improved service quality and operational efficiency. Similarly, Vitamog and Tactay (2012) emphasized that proper waste management practices are essential in maintaining sanitation, environmental compliance, and sustainable canteen operations.

Despite these guidelines and findings, many school canteens continue to experience difficulties in fully implementing quality service standards and sustaining efficient operations. Common problems include inadequate inventory and financial management, limited staff training, poor monitoring mechanisms, absence of systematic customer feedback procedures, and lack of innovative operational strategies. As a result, these challenges often lead to inefficient service delivery, food wastage, financial instability, customer dissatisfaction, and inconsistent compliance with DepEd standards. Moreover, the diverse needs and preferences of learners and teachers require school canteens to adopt innovative approaches that enhance customer satisfaction while ensuring income sustainability and operational efficiency.

In relation to this, several studies have explored food safety compliance, nutrition programs, and operational practices in school canteens. Fabre and Pacpaco (2020) found that proper management and operational practices significantly influence food safety, nutrition services, and operational effectiveness, which may serve as a basis for enhanced canteen development programs. Similarly, Cadiente (2024) emphasized that there remains limited research on sustainable food practices and policy effectiveness in public school canteens, particularly in the Philippine setting, where operational sustainability and policy implementation still require further assessment.

Even so, there remains a limited body of research focusing specifically on the implementation of best practices and innovations that can deliver quality service, sustain income, and strengthen canteen operations within the context of public secondary schools. Additionally, there is a scarcity of localized empirical evidence examining how these strategies are implemented in rural or integrated public schools such as Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School. This gap affirms the need for a contextualized assessment aimed at improving, strengthening, sustaining, and institutionalizing school canteen best practices and innovative strategies.

In this regard, the researcher deemed it necessary to conduct this study to assess the extent of implementation of best practices and innovations in the canteen of Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School. The findings of this study may serve as a basis for action planning, operational improvement, long-term

sustainability, and future innovation initiatives in school canteen management and operation.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine and assess the extent of the implementation of school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and sustaining income and operation at Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School, Baras, Rizal.

The findings of this study shall serve as a basis for the formulation of a proposed action plan focused on strengthening, sustaining, and institutionalizing school canteen best practices and innovations, consistent with the principles of school-based management and continuous improvement.

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service, sustaining income, and ensuring efficient operation with respect to?
 - 1.1 compliance to food safety standards;
 - 1.2 daily operations and financial management;
 - 1.3 7s embedded canteen;
 - 1.4 data-based inventory system;
 - 1.5 VOC-based system;
 - 1.6 reward and incentive system;
 - 1.7 recognition system;
 - 1.8 canteen gift certificates;
 - 1.9 loyalty and discount cards;
 - 1.10 satellite canteen system; and
 - 1.11 Project Online Canteen Report System (OCRS)?
2. What are the comments and suggestions of the students, teachers, and parents to further improve canteen services?
3. What is the comparative analysis of the canteen's net sales during School Year 2023–2024 and School Year 2024–2025 with the implementation of best practices and innovations?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed to further strengthen, sustain, and institutionalize the implementation of school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and sustaining income and operations?

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on the best practices and innovations implemented in the school canteen of Baras Pinugay Integrated High School during School Years 2023–2024. It aimed to assess the extent to which these practices such as compliance to food safety standards; daily operations and financial management; 7s embedded canteen; data-based inventory system; VOC-based system; reward and incentive system; recognition system; canteen gift certificate; loyalty and discount cards; satellite canteen system; and Project Online Canteen Report System (OCRS) that have contributed to delivering quality service, sustaining income and ensure efficient canteen operation.

The study incorporated the Voice of the Customer (VOC) by collecting input, remarks, and recommendations from students, teachers, and parents to enhance canteen services further. Additionally, a comparative assessment of the canteen's net income for SY 2023–2024 and SY 2024–2025 will be performed to appraise the financial effects of the implemented strategies and innovations. The participants were purposively selected which include selected students who are classroom and SSLG Officers, PTA parent-officers, and teachers of Baras Pinugay Integrated High School who are directly involved with or

influenced by the canteen services. This study is specifically focused on the operations and performance of the Baras Pinugay Integrated High School canteen.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Systems theory, Total Quality Management (TQM) principles, and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation.

Systems theory (Von Bertalanffy, 1968) stressed that an organization functions as an interrelated and interdependent system, where each component affects the overall performance. In the context of the school canteen, various components such as compliance to food safety standards, daily operations, inventory management, customer feedback systems, reward systems, and technological innovations which operate as interconnected subsystems. Efficient performance in one area, such as inventory management, directly influences the overall effectiveness, income sustainability, and quality of service of the canteen. This theory was relevant in the study because it stressed the importance of an integrated approach, where improvements in one subsystem contribute to the holistic success of canteen operations.

In addition, Total Quality Management (TQM) principles (Deming, 1986) emphasize continuous improvement, stakeholder satisfaction, and systematic problem-solving to enhance service quality. Applying TQM in the school canteen encourages adherence to food safety standards, operational excellence, systematic financial tracking, and responsive feedback mechanisms. The implementation of innovations, such as the Online Canteen Reporting System and satellite canteen stations, reflects the continuous improvement philosophy of TQM, ensuring operational efficiency, quality service, and sustainable income.

Furthermore, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation (Herzberg, Mausner, & Snyderman, 1959) differentiates between hygiene factors, such as safe working conditions and organizational policies, and motivators, such as recognition and rewards, in influencing employee satisfaction and performance. The canteen's reward and incentive systems, recognition practices, and gift certificates act as motivators that enhance staff performance and commitment, while hygiene factors like compliance with food safety standards and organized operations ensure a safe and conducive working environment. This theory was relevant to the study because it explained how human-centered practices influence operational efficiency, stakeholder satisfaction, and income sustainability.

By integrating these three theories, the study provided a comprehensive framework to assess the extent of the implementation of canteen best practices and innovations. Systems theory underscored the importance of interconnected practices, TQM principles guided the evaluation of quality service and operational efficiency, and Herzberg's motivation theory explained the role of recognition and rewards in sustaining staff performance. These frameworks were relevant as the study's focus on both operational and human-centered practices to ensure quality service, sustainable income, and efficient operations in the school canteen.

Review of Related Literature

Best Practices

Best practices in school canteen management refer to standardized procedures and strategies that ensure safe, efficient, and sustainable operations. These practices are essential in maintaining food safety, improving service quality, and ensuring customer satisfaction among stakeholders.

One of the most important best practices is food safety and sanitation management. Proper food handling, preparation, storage, and hygiene practices help prevent contamination and foodborne diseases. Strict compliance with sanitation standards in food preparation areas is emphasized as a critical component of safe school food service operations (Alders et al., 2018).

Another key best practice is proper menu planning and nutrition management. School canteens are encouraged to serve balanced, safe, and affordable meals that support students' health and learning capacity. Providing nutritious meals contributes to improved student performance and well-being (Brown & Martin,

2020).

In addition, financial management and inventory control are essential best practices in canteen operations. Proper budgeting, monitoring of supplies, and accurate financial record-keeping help ensure sustainability and prevent wastage of resources (Montano & Reyes, 2022).

Moreover, human resource management and staff training are important in maintaining consistent service quality. Trained personnel ensure proper food handling, efficient service delivery, and better customer relations, which are crucial in maintaining a well-functioning canteen system (FAO, 2019).

Lastly, stakeholder engagement and feedback mechanisms are also considered best practices. Involving students, teachers, and parents in evaluating canteen services helps improve operations and ensures that services meet user needs (WHO, 2020).

Innovations

Innovations in school canteen management involve the introduction of new technologies, systems, and strategies that improve efficiency, service delivery, and sustainability.

One major innovation is the use of digital systems in canteen operations, such as electronic ordering, cashless payment methods, and digital inventory tracking. These technologies improve transaction efficiency, reduce errors, and enhance customer convenience (Harris & Bargh, 2021).

Another innovation is the use of social media and digital marketing tools to promote canteen products and services. This allows canteens to communicate menus, gather feedback, and engage with students more effectively, leading to improved customer satisfaction and participation.

The development of healthier and diversified menu innovations is also a significant advancement. Many school canteens are now introducing nutritious food options such as low-sugar, low-fat, and locally sourced meals to support healthier eating habits among students (Brown & Martin, 2020).

In addition, process innovations in food preparation and service delivery such as standardized recipes, improved workflow systems, and faster serving methods contribute to greater operational efficiency and reduced waiting time (Gustafsson & Hall, 2019).

Finally, sustainability innovations, including waste reduction programs, eco-friendly packaging, and recycling initiatives, are being implemented in school canteens to promote environmental responsibility and long-term operational sustainability (WHO, 2020).

Compliance to food safety standards

Compliance to food safety standards refers to the strict observance of policies, guidelines, and practices that ensure the safety, quality, and nutritional value of food served in school canteens. It encompasses proper food handling, hygiene, sanitation, storage, preparation, and adherence to government regulations such as DepEd Orders No. 8, s. 2007 and No. 13, s. 2017, which mandate safe and nutritious meals in Philippine schools. High compliance not only protects the health of students but also supports sustainable school operations and promotes trust among stakeholders. Several studies have examined the level of compliance with food safety standards in schools.

Lampitoc (2019) found that public school canteen managers in Batac City were very much aware of and generally always compliant with food management, operational, and accounting policies outlined in DepEd orders. Similarly, a study on canteen food handlers in the District of Maria, Siquijor revealed that their food safety knowledge, attitudes, and practices were rated very high, particularly in safe food handling and preparation, indicating strong adherence to safety standards in the local context (Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives, n.d.).

However, gaps remain in the consistent enforcement of these standards. Facundo et al. (2017) highlighted that while DepEd's school food policies are comprehensive, their implementation and monitoring remain weak due to insufficient training, resource limitations, and lack of systematic enforcement. This echoes findings from Naga City, where most schools complied with basic safety

provisions such as safe water, handwashing facilities, and clean utensils but showed lower compliance with more specific directives, including nutritional food restrictions and vendor management (ResearchGate, n.d.). These studies suggest that while basic food safety practices are “very much practice,” stricter and more nuanced standards require stronger monitoring and institutional support to ensure full compliance

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has mandated the promotion of healthy eating and safe food handling through DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2017 (Policy and Guidelines on Healthy Food and Beverage Choices in Schools and in DepEd Offices) and DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2007 (Revised Implementing Guidelines on the Operation and Management of School Canteens). These policies serve as the foundation for school canteen practices, requiring the elimination of junk food, training of food handlers, and the regular inspection of food items. Compliance with these policies ensures that canteen operations are aligned with national goals for child health, safety, and nutrition (DepEd, 2017).

Research by Santos and Cruz (2020) on public school canteens in the Philippines emphasized that strict adherence to food safety protocols significantly reduces health risks and builds trust among stakeholders.

Several studies emphasize the importance of establishing structured systems in school canteens to promote efficiency and transparency. These include the use of food safety management systems, staff hygiene protocols, and proper supplier accreditation processes (Galvez & Flores, 2021).

Daily operations and financial management

Daily operations and financial management in canteens refer to the systematic planning, organization, recording, and monitoring of everyday processes and monetary activities. This includes managing sales, expenses, inventory, procurement, pricing, and the submission of financial reports. Effective operations ensure timely service, cost control, and consistent quality, while sound financial management supports transparency, sustainability, and informed decision-making.

A study by Fabre and Pacpaco (2020) investigated the management and operational status of school canteens in selected public secondary schools in Ilocos Sur. Using a descriptive-correlational design, their study found that the overall status of canteen management and operations was “High.” This reflects strong daily practices in areas such as food preparation, cost management, facilities, and nutrition planning.

Additionally, Ubalde et al. (2023) assessed service operations in Mabolo National High School and reported elevated levels of student satisfaction with canteen services. The study emphasized operational efficiency and responsiveness which are critical components of effective daily management.

In Tarlac City District 8, another study explored canteen management and financial intervention in public elementary schools. It assessed financial aspects like sources and uses of funds, profit viability, and transparency (as perceived by teachers, students, and canteen personnel). The study implied that robust financial practices that includes clear accounting and financial transparency are vital for improving canteen services.

Moreover, DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2007 and No. 13, s. 2017 provide clear guidelines for canteen operations, especially regarding the maintenance of daily books of account and auditing procedures (DepEd, n.d.).

7S Embedded canteen

7S Embedded Canteen Practices emphasize the principles of Sort, Set in Order, Shine, Standardize, Sustain, Safety, and Spirituality. These practices are designed to promote efficiency, cleanliness, orderliness, and sustained discipline in canteen operations.

Psmas and Deliou (2024) highlighted that lean manufacturing practices such as 5S, visual management, and standardization are among the most adopted methods in food manufacturing companies in Greece. Their study revealed that while these practices are highly implemented, the challenge lies in sustaining them alongside technological integration.

Similarly, Widiwati, Liman, and Nurprihatin (2024) demonstrated through a Lean Six Sigma (LSS)

approach that systematic housekeeping tools, when combined with structured problem-solving techniques like DMAIC, effectively reduce waste and improve quality in food manufacturing industries.

A Study by Villanueva (2019) demonstrated that integrating the 7S principles in school canteens enhanced cleanliness, minimized waste, and streamlined processes, resulting in higher customer satisfaction.

The application of the 7S methodology (Sort, Set in Order, Shine, Standardize, Sustain, Safety, and Spirit) in canteen management has also shown positive effects on cleanliness, productivity, and customer satisfaction (Santos & Reyes, 2020).

Data-based inventory system

A data-based inventory system is a digital stock-control approach that records every stock-in/stock-out transaction in a structured database and typically integrates tools like barcodes, point-of-sale (POS), and dashboards to deliver real-time counts, expiry monitoring, and automated reports for decision-making.

In the school-canteen context, early Philippine work by Bastan, Hopelos, Jalbuena, Medianero, Octaviano, and Pescuela (2004) at Central Philippine University designed a Computerized Satellite Canteen Sales and Inventory System that centralized multiple stations' sales and stocks. Their system demonstrated how database capture improves traceability and reporting across satellite canteens, exactly the kind of capability schools need when they operate several serving points.

Moving from general computerization to contactless automation, Espinosa, Lumibao, Zerrudo, and Intal (2021) at Mapúa University engineered an RFID-enabled, cashless canteen system. Beyond faster queues, their design tied payment events to instant stock updates reducing manual encoding and improving accuracy for perishable items common in school menus.

Laping, Mendoza, Tiulentino, Villaraza, Bucu, and Ngo (2023) at the University of Santo Tomas applied a design-thinking method to build a user-centered, SaaS inventory system for a convenience store handling perishable. Users preferred the prototype that delivered real-time sales/stock visibility and easier monitoring of "bad merchandise" (expired/near-expiry), underscoring that effective database design should foreground usability, rapid updating, and shelf-life controls, needs that map closely to canteen operations.

Voice of the Customer (VOC)-based system

The Voice of the Customer (VOC) refers to systematically gathering and analyzing feedback, preferences, expectations, and satisfaction from customers like students, teachers, parents, and staff to inform service improvements. In school canteens, implementing VOC-based systems involves using tools like feedback terminals, rating systems, surveys, preordering interfaces, and digital dashboards to collect real-time input and drive enhancements in food quality, service speed, and overall satisfaction.

Recent innovations in VOC-driven canteen solutions include CafeCampus, a smart canteen platform designed with feedback and preordering features. Users can rate dishes and leave comments while ordering ahead of time, helping reduce wait times and enabling canteen operators to adjust menu offerings and service flow based on student preferences (CafeCampus: Smart Canteen Food Rating and Preorder System, n.d.).

In parallel, Cano and Hijada II (2024) conducted a mixed-method study in Davao City and found that high levels of canteen service quality measured through tangibility, responsiveness, and empathy correlated strongly with customer satisfaction. This indicates that VOC inputs, whether via structured instruments or informal feedback, play a significant role in maintaining quality service in school canteens.

Expanding beyond canteens, in food service settings more broadly, Budiningsari et al. (2023)

demonstrated that implementing a customer satisfaction survey along with menu development and HACCP training led to noticeable improvements in canteen food service quality highlighting how listening to customer feedback aids in enhancing product variety, training focus, and service standards.

Effective canteen management is not only administrative but participatory. Gathering feedback from students, parents, and teachers is a cornerstone of customer-centered service improvement. Research by Javier & Ramos (2021) highlighted how customer feedback helped school canteens identify gaps in service and develop more responsive practices. Through surveys, suggestion boxes, and consultations, stakeholder involvement ensures that canteen operations align with the actual needs and preferences of the school community.

A study by Tan and Reyes (2020) underscored the importance of incorporating customer feedback in canteen operations. Their research revealed that using Voice of Customer (VOC) systems to gather and act on feedback significantly improved service quality and customer satisfaction.

Reward and incentive system

A reward and incentive system in a school canteen spans two fronts: (1) employee-focused recognition and rewards (e.g., performance bonuses, public recognition, gift certificates, free meals) to motivate service staff, and (2) customer-focused incentives (e.g., loyalty cards, discounts, point-based rewards) to encourage repeat patronage and healthy purchasing.

A recent PRISMA-guided systematic review by Vargas-Diez et al. (2024) synthesized 61 studies and concluded that well-designed reward systems are powerful levers for shaping workplace behavior, improving performance, and aligning individual actions with organizational goals, evidence that supports instituting formal, documented canteen staff reward and recognition programs (e.g., monthly awards, merit-based bonuses). In parallel, Uslu et al. (2025) found that recognition, perceived fairness, and leadership significantly predict employee engagement and job performance; recognition had a direct, positive effect, suggesting that low-cost, high-visibility practices (e.g., posting commendations, certificates with small gift vouchers) can lift morale and consistency in daily service quality).

On the customer side, Schuhmann and Kwornik (2019) and subsequent loyalty research summarized by Sharp et al. (2017) show that loyalty programs reliably increase retention and repeat purchasing by delivering utilitarian (discounts, freebies) and delightful (fun, status) benefits; a 2023–2024 overview of loyalty-card effects further documents measurable shifts in customer behavior (higher visit frequency, basket size) when rewards are salient and easy to redeem directly applicable to canteen loyalty/discount cards and gift certificates tied to healthy choices or good conduct in queues.

Complementary cafeteria evidence from Thorndike et al. (2014) indicates that price/cost incentives and salient education cues can nudge customers toward healthier options useful for designing canteen rewards that privilege nutritious items (e.g., stamp cards that unlock discounts on “green-tag” meals).

Recognition system

A recognition system is a structured approach by which organizations formally acknowledge, appreciate, and reward employees or stakeholders for their contributions, performance, or desirable behaviors. Recognition is distinct from monetary rewards because it emphasizes intrinsic motivation, acknowledgment, and appreciation as drivers of sustained engagement.

According to Brun and Dugas (2008), recognition plays four critical roles: personal, work practice, job dedication, and results recognition, all of which contribute to increased employee morale and performance. This framework underlines the importance of embedding recognition into daily routines in service organizations such as school canteens, where frontline workers interact directly with customers.

Recent empirical findings confirm recognition’s impact on work outcomes. Uslu et al. (2025) demonstrated that recognition has a direct positive effect on both employee engagement and job performance, alongside fairness and leadership. Their study suggests that recognition does not need to be

costly but must be consistent, transparent, and aligned with performance criteria, such as acknowledging punctuality, teamwork, and excellent service in canteen operations.

Similarly, Ghosh et al. (2016) found that organizations with strong recognition systems experienced higher employee motivation, lower turnover, and greater organizational commitment, reinforcing the idea that appreciation is a cost-effective tool in sustaining quality service delivery. Recognition systems also extend to customer-facing practices.

In the school canteen context, Thorndike et al. (2014) highlighted that when cafeterias provided salient acknowledgment and feedback (e.g., labeling, social recognition of healthy choices), customers, students in this case were more likely to engage in desired behaviors, such as choosing healthier meals.

The literature strongly supports the integration of a recognition system in school canteens as both an employee motivator and a behavioral management tool. When staff are recognized for excellent service, they sustain morale and consistency; when students/customers are acknowledged for desirable choices, healthier habits and positive conduct are reinforced. Together, these recognition practices enhance service quality, customer satisfaction, and operational sustainability.

Canteen gift certificates

Canteen gift certificates are non-cash, redeemable vouchers issued to customers and staff as incentives, offering flexibility to choose items while reinforcing positive behavior such as loyalty or healthy choices. Their effectiveness stems from psychological mechanisms including perceived autonomy, valued ownership, and increased spending. Psychological and marketing research consistently highlights that gift cards outperform standard discounts.

As detailed by Ncentiva (2025), gift cards hold higher perceived value than flat discounts because they offer flexibility and a sense of personal appreciation. They also trigger emotional responses such as dopamine release that encourage repeat purchases and foster goodwill toward the issuer. In the school canteen environment, gift certificates especially when tied to healthy food purchases or loyalty can similarly boost patronage and behavioral engagement.

These studies indicate that canteen gift certificates are a strong tool for encouraging desirable behaviors if they are designed for high perceived value, redemption ease, and alignment with goals like health or loyalty, and used strategically to avoid devaluing intrinsic enjoyment

Loyalty and discount cards

Loyalty and discount cards are widely used tools in marketing and service management to strengthen customer retention, encourage repeat patronage, and build long-term relationships. They function by offering incentives such as discounts, points, or exclusive benefits, which foster both economic and emotional bonds between organizations and customers.

According to Sharp and Sharp (1997), loyalty programs help increase purchase frequency and improve customer retention, though their effectiveness depends on perceived value and ease of redemption. This suggests that when implemented in canteen settings, loyalty cards could promote habitual purchases and stable revenue streams.

In the food service context, Meyer-Waarden (2008) found that loyalty programs positively influenced consumer behavior by increasing repeat patronage and strengthening the psychological commitment of customers to the brand. In schools or workplace canteens, this translates to students or employees consistently choosing the institutional canteen over external vendors when loyalty rewards are perceived as attractive and attainable.

Discount cards, meanwhile, have been shown to alter short-term consumption behavior. Taylor and Neslin (2005) revealed that price promotions, including discount cards, significantly increase immediate sales, although they may not always guarantee long-term loyalty. However, when paired with a loyalty structure, discount cards can create a dual effect stimulating instant spending while gradually building long-term relationships. In canteens, this may involve offering students or staff discounts on healthier options, thereby encouraging better dietary habits and sustained patronage.

Finally, the rise of digital loyalty cards and apps has expanded accessibility and tracking efficiency. Demoulin and Zidda (2009) observed that personalization and digital integration enhance customer perceptions of fairness and convenience, leading to higher satisfaction and greater engagement. When adapted for canteens, digital loyalty and discount systems can streamline operations, track consumption patterns, and sustain income while improving customer experience.

The literature shows that loyalty and discount cards enhance both immediate and sustained patronage, especially when designed with customer convenience, fairness, and perceived value in mind. Applied in canteens, they can promote repeat purchases, healthier choices, and financial sustainability, while also fostering stronger connections between the institution and its stakeholders

Satellite canteen system

A Satellite Canteen System refers to multiple dispersed food service outlets or mini-canteens strategically placed across a school campus (e.g., by floor or building wing) to enhance accessibility, reduce congestion, and improve service efficiency. These mini-outlets typically adhere to the same quality standards and menus as the main canteen but operate at separate locations.

In a study conducted at Ateneo de Davao University's Finster Building, Beluan, et.al. (2019) investigated Grade 12 learners' satisfaction with satellite canteen services. The findings revealed that key satisfaction dimensions such as food quality, staff performance, and price fairness varied across different mini-canteens, suggesting that localized operational conditions significantly influence student perceptions.

Galabo (2019) examined correlations between perceived service quality and student satisfaction in a Philippine setting. Results indicated that tangible factors like facilities, orderliness, and staff responsiveness are strong predictors of satisfaction, elements that satellite canteens must replicate consistently across all nodes to maintain overall service quality.

From a management perspective, Nicodemus and Versano (2022) explored school cafeteria management and customer satisfaction in Mulanay District II. While not explicitly about satellites, their findings emphasized that effective canteen management—encompassing food safety, utensil handling, service quality, and facility usage is directly correlated with customer satisfaction. These operational standards are critical to maintain across all satellite outlets to ensure uniformity and quality service.

These studies affirm that satellite canteen systems can enhance student accessibility and reduce crowding, but their success depends on uniform quality across locations. Key factors such as food quality, service responsiveness, facility maintenance, and fair pricing must be consistently managed to sustain high customer satisfaction across all satellite nodes.

Online Canteen Report System (OCRS)

An Online Canteen Reporting System (OCRS) refers to digital platforms or software designed to streamline canteen operations by automating data collection, report generation, and monitoring of finances and inventory. These systems reduce manual workload, improve accuracy, and provide decision-makers with timely insights into operational and financial performance.

One of the earliest documented examples in the Philippine context is the Computerized Canteen Sales Reporting (CCSR) system developed by Peralta (2019). Built in Microsoft Excel, CCSR transformed daily sales and profit reporting into a streamlined process, reducing report preparation time from nearly two hours to just 30–45 minutes—a 75% efficiency gain. Peralta's study also found that the improved accuracy and reduced administrative burden allowed canteen managers to redirect effort toward management and quality tasks highlighting both operational and financial benefits.

Extending the concept of digital reporting, Justine (2024) developed a fully web-based canteen management system for Uganda Martyrs University (Masaka Campus). This system integrated online operations including ordering and reporting within a scalable web architecture. The project showcased how digitally enabled systems can address key challenges such as queue management, order tracking, and transaction transparency in institutional cafeterias.

Further innovations include the QR-based Canteen Management System designed by Bhattarai et

al. (2024). This system utilized QR codes for cashless transactions and integrated automated sales recording. It notably reduced inefficiencies found in traditional pen-and-paper methods while improving ordering speed and record accuracy, two essential functions of an effective OCRS.

Complementing these case studies, Fegade et al. (2019) reviewed various canteen automation systems, including mobile apps that facilitate e-wallet payments, real-time inventory tracking, and administrative analytics. The study concluded that such technology-enabled infrastructures significantly boost operational transparency, customer satisfaction, and scalability across institutional settings.

Comparative Analysis

Comparative analysis of canteen sales offers valuable insights into differences in product offerings, profitability, and operational models essential for informing improvements in service and income strategies.

A notable study by de Oliveira et al. (2023) conducted a detailed comparison of traditional versus healthy model private school canteens. They found that traditional canteens averaged more items sold (40 vs. 33), a higher number of students served (>500 vs. 300–500), and greater profit margins (often exceeding 100% for best-selling products) compared to their healthy-model counterparts. Although initial investment recovery was faster in healthy-model canteens, traditional ones showed robust volume-based profitability. This suggests a trade-off: while healthy practices may yield quicker returns on investment, traditional models may generate stronger overall revenue due to volume and high-margin items.

In contrast, Posch et al. (2020) demonstrated a data-driven forecasting approach for food and beverage sales using time-series models based on POS data from a staff canteen. Their Bayesian generalized additive models accurately predicted daily item sales, accommodating patterns like seasonality and trends. This forecasting capability helps managers fine-tune stock ordering and reduce waste, elements crucial for effective comparative analysis between different canteen models or times.

On the consumer side, Ariston et al. (n.d.) compared students' expenses when bringing packed meals versus purchasing from the canteen. The findings showed that buying from the canteen cost students a daily average of ₱29–₱53 more than bringing packed food. These results provide a key comparative benchmark for customers' spending behavior and can inform pricing, menu, and promotional strategies to align cost perceptions with value.

Research Method

This research study utilized a descriptive research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative techniques.

The quantitative aspect includes a validated researcher-made questionnaire-checklist that employs a 5-point Likert scale to assess the level of implementation of best practices and innovations.

The qualitative research method features open-ended questions and an analysis of feedback to gather comments, suggestions, and insights from various stakeholders (students, teachers, and parents). This methodology facilitates a thorough understanding of both quantifiable results and contextual experiences.

Research Locale

The research took place at Baras Pinugay Integrated High School, a public secondary institution governed by the Department of Education, situated in Brgy. Pinugay, Baras, Rizal. The canteen of the school has implemented a range of best practices and innovations during the School Years 2023–2024 and 2024–2025, which serve as the foundation for this study.

Population and Sampling

The participants in the study consisted of students, teachers, and parents who have direct involvement or are impacted by the school canteen. A purposive sampling method will be employed to choose individuals who frequently use or observe the canteen's operations. The projected number of participants includes: 300 students from different grade levels, 70 teachers, and 30 parents. These participants are deemed to be rich sources of information that can offer valuable insights based on their experiences and observations.

Research Instrument

The primary tool is a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist consisting of two sections: 1. Section I – Quantitative Part: A checklist utilizing a 5-point Likert Scale (Very Much Practice, Much Practice, Sometimes Practice, Less Practice, Not Practice at All), assessing aspects such as: compliance to food safety standards; daily operations and financial management; 7s embedded canteen; data-based inventory system; VOC-based system; reward and incentive system; recognition system; canteen gift certificate; loyalty and discount cards; satellite canteen system; and Project Online Canteen Report System (OCRS).

Section II – Qualitative Part: Open-ended questions aimed at gathering feedback and suggestions for improving and sustaining the canteen service. Furthermore, financial documents (sales reports and net income statements) from SY 2023–2024 and SY 2024–2025 will be examined for comparative assessment.

Data Gathering Procedure

Approval to carry out the study was obtained from the principal of the school. Once the approval is granted, the researcher distributed the validated questionnaire with selected respondents. Data was collected using printed forms and/or Google Forms to ensure accessibility. Emphasis was placed on confidentiality and voluntary participation. Financial records were sourced from the school canteen manager with appropriate consent secured. All the data gathered were treated with utmost confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, particularly the **mean**, to determine the extent of implementation of school canteen best practices and innovations. The mean scores were interpreted using a scale to describe the level of practice and implementation.

For the qualitative data, responses from students, parents, and teachers were subjected to **thematic analysis**. Comments and suggestions were carefully reviewed, coded, and categorized to identify recurring themes, stakeholder perceptions, and key areas for improvement. This process allowed for the identification of common concerns and recommendations related to canteen operations and service quality.

In addition, a **comparative analysis** was conducted on the canteen's net sales across two consecutive school years. This involved the computation of **percentage change** and examination of **trend patterns** to assess financial performance, growth, or decline in income. The analysis provided evidence of the sustainability and effectiveness of the implemented practices and innovations.

Finally, based on the synthesis of quantitative and qualitative findings, an **action plan was formulated** to further strengthen, sustain, and institutionalize the identified best practices and innovations. The plan aims to enhance service quality, improve operational efficiency, and ensure long-term financial sustainability of the school canteen.

Results and Discussion

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to compliance to food safety standards;

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Compliance to Food Safety Standards		
1. Canteen staff wear complete PPE (hairnet, mask, gloves, apron).	4.92	Very Much Practice
2. Color-coded knives and chopping boards are used to prevent cross-contamination.	4.88	Very Much Practice
3. Food handlers receive training on food safety and hygiene practices.	4.90	Very Much Practice
4. Proper food handling, storage, and preparation is consistently observed.	4.86	Very Much Practice
5. The canteen has updated sanitary and business permits.	5.00	Very Much Practice
6. Food handlers have updated health certificates.	5.00	Very Much Practice
7. Food suppliers comply with food safety and quality standards.	4.94	Very Much Practice
8. Canteen is strict compliant to DepEd Order No. 13, s.2017 on the Healthy Food and Beverage Choices.	4.87	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.92	Very Much Practice

4.81-5.00 Very much practice; 3.81-4.80 Much practice; 2.81-3.80 Sometimes practice; 1.81-2.80 Less practice; 1.00-1.80 Not practice

It can be gleaned from the table that Compliance to Food Safety Standards in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.92, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. Each indicator reflects strong adherence to policies and procedures that ensure safe and hygienic food service specifically: Canteen staff wear complete PPE (hairnet, mask, gloves, apron) received a mean of 4.92, indicating strict enforcement of protective clothing for all food handlers to minimize contamination risks, Color-coded knives and chopping boards scored 4.88, demonstrating effective measures to prevent cross-contamination, Food handlers receive training on food safety and hygiene practices earned 4.90, highlighting consistent staff education on health and safety standards, Proper food handling, storage, and preparation is consistently observed obtained 4.86, reflecting systematic monitoring and adherence to safe food practices, The canteen has updated sanitary and business permits and food handlers have updated health certificates both scored 5.00 which ranked first, showing strict compliance with regulatory requirements, Food suppliers comply with food safety and quality standards scored 4.94, indicating careful selection of certified suppliers, and canteen is strictly compliant with DepEd Order No. 13, Series of 2017 on healthy food and beverage choices obtained 4.87, demonstrating alignment with government-mandated nutrition policies. The overall grand mean of 4.92 indicates that these best practices are Very Much Practice, reflecting the canteen's commitment to student health and well-being, operational efficiency, and regulatory compliance.

The result of the study aligns with Peralta (2019) emphasizes that strict adherence to food safety protocols, including proper PPE and handling, reduces contamination risks and safeguards student health. Justine (2024) and Bhattarai et al. (2024) highlight that implementing structured hygiene systems and using certified suppliers ensure operational safety and food quality. Ncentiva (2025) and Fegade et al. (2019) demonstrate that continuous staff training and alignment with government nutrition policies improve service quality and health outcomes.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to daily operations and financial management;

Daily Operations and Financial Management		
1. The canteen follows a systematic flow of daily operations.	4.83	Very Much Practice
2. Financial records are transparent and updated (daily (sales, expenses, inventory)).	4.92	Very Much Practice
3. A documented system of monitoring income and expenses is in place.	4.87	Very Much Practice
4. Reports are submitted regularly to the School Canteen Auditing Committee.	4.95	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.89	Very Much Practice

The table shows that Daily Operations and Financial Management in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.89, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. The indicators reflect that the canteen maintains a systematic and efficient management structure that ensures smooth daily operations, accurate financial tracking, and accountability. Specifically: 1. The canteen follows a systematic flow of daily operations received a mean of 4.83, indicating well-organized processes that ensure efficiency in food preparation, service, and management. 2. Financial records are updated daily (sales, expenses, and inventory) scored 4.92, reflecting consistent monitoring and maintenance of accurate financial data. 3. A documented system of monitoring income and expenses is in place earned 4.87, showing that the canteen implements structured tracking mechanisms for transparency and operational control. 4. Reports are submitted regularly to the School Canteen Committee obtained 4.95, highlighting adherence to accountability practices and timely communication of financial and operational status.

The overall grand mean of 4.89 demonstrates that the canteen's operational and financial management practices are Very Much Practice, indicating a strong culture of efficiency, organization, and accountability that supports sustainable operations and quality service delivery.

The study is aligned with Ghosh et al. (2016) emphasize that systematic operational workflows and structured record-keeping in school canteens improve efficiency and ensure accurate tracking of income and expenses. Bhattarai et al. (2024) report that documented monitoring systems and regular reporting enhance transparency and informed decision-making in school-based operations. Justine (2024) highlights that maintaining updated financial and inventory records is crucial for operational efficiency and sustainability in educational institutions.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operations with respect to 7s embedded canteen;

7S Embedded Canteen		
1. The canteen practices the 7S (Sort, Set in Order, Shine, Standardize, Sustain, Safety, Spirituality).	4.87	Very much Practice
2. Cleanliness and orderliness are maintained at all times.	4.92	Very Much Practice
3. Visual management and labeling are used in food preparation areas.	4.78	Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.86	Very Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the 7S Embedded Canteen practices in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School are highly observed, with an overall grand mean of 4.86, verbally interpreted as

Very Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen effectively integrates principles of Sort, Set in Order, Shine, Standardize, Sustain, Safety, and Spirituality (7S) to maintain organization, cleanliness, and efficiency in daily operations. Specifically: 1. The canteen practices the 7S received a mean of 4.87, showing that the principles of workplace organization and standardization are consistently implemented. 2. Cleanliness and orderliness are maintained at all times scored 4.92, reflecting the canteen's strong commitment to hygiene, proper arrangement, and safe working environments. 3. Visual management and labeling are used in food preparation areas earned 4.78, indicating that while labeling and visual cues are implemented, there is room for further improvement to enhance clarity and accessibility for staff.

The overall grand mean of 4.86 demonstrates that the 7S methodology is Very Much Practiced, creating a clean, safe, and efficient canteen environment that promotes both staff and student satisfaction. This structured approach supports operational efficiency and helps maintain high standards in food preparation and service.

The result is supported by Anchieta (2019) emphasizes that applying workplace organization systems, such as the 7S framework, improves operational efficiency, cleanliness, and employee adherence to procedures in school cafeterias. Bhattarai et al. (2024) note that systematic cleanliness and visual management enhance workflow, minimize errors, and maintain high standards in food service operations.

The result conforms to Fegade et al. (2019) highlight that labeling and visual cues in food preparation areas support safety and operational efficiency by clearly communicating instructions and reducing contamination risks.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to data-based inventory system;

Data-based Inventory System		
1. The canteen uses a digital and manual inventory system.	4.94	Very Much Practice
2. Daily stock-in and stock-out of supplies are properly recorded	5.00	Very Much Practice
3. Inventory reports are updated and submitted regularly.	4.83	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.92	Very Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Database Inventory System in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.92, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen effectively maintains accurate and systematic records of supplies, ensuring operational efficiency, proper stock management, and accountability. Specifically: 1. The canteen continues to use a digital and manual inventory system received a mean of 4.94, showing that both traditional and technological methods are employed to ensure reliability and accessibility of inventory data. 2. Daily stock-in and stock-out of supplies are properly recorded scored 5.00, reflecting consistent monitoring of stock levels, preventing shortages or overstocking, and ensuring timely replenishment. 3. Inventory reports are updated and submitted regularly earned 4.83, indicating that reporting is systematic and transparent, supporting informed decision-making by canteen management.

The overall grand mean of 4.92 demonstrates that inventory management practices are Very Much Practice, contributing to operational efficiency, financial accountability, and sustained service quality in the canteen. Proper inventory management minimizes waste, enhances cost control, and ensures that students consistently receive safe and high-quality food.

The result aligns with Justine (2024) emphasizes that implementing both digital and manual inventory systems in school canteens improves accuracy, minimizes errors, and supports efficient stock monitoring.

Moreover, the result is supported by Bhattarai et al. (2024) note that daily recording of stock-in and stock-out transactions and regular reporting ensures transparency, operational continuity, and informed

managerial decisions.

Ghosh et al. (2016) highlight that structured inventory and reporting systems improve accountability, cost control, and overall efficiency in institutional food services.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to VOC-based system;

VOC-Based System (Voice of the Customer)		
1. Feedback from students, teachers, and parents is collected regularly.	4.78	Much Practice
2. The canteen responds to customer suggestions and concerns.	4.80	Much Practice
3. There are available feedback or suggestion forms/boxes.	4.20	Much Practice
4. Customer feedback is used to improve canteen operations.	4.74	Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.63	Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Voice of the Customer (VOC)-Based System in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is moderately observed, with a grand mean of 4.63, verbally interpreted as Much Practice. This indicates that while the canteen collects and responds to stakeholder feedback, there is still room for strengthening the system to maximize customer engagement and service improvement. Specifically: 1. Feedback from students, teachers, and parents is collected regularly received a mean of 4.78, showing that the canteen seeks input from stakeholders but could increase the frequency or method of collection for broader participation. 2. Continuous response to customer suggestions and concerns scored 4.80, reflecting a proactive approach in addressing feedback, though further systematic follow-up may enhance responsiveness. 3. Availability of feedback or suggestion forms/boxes earned 4.20, indicating that while tools for feedback exist, accessibility and usage could be improved to ensure that more stakeholders actively provide suggestions. 4. Customer feedback is used to improve continuous operations obtained 4.74, demonstrating that suggestions are considered in decision-making, but the system may not yet be fully optimized for continuous quality improvement.

The overall grand mean of 4.63 demonstrates that VOC practices are Much Practice, signifying a canteen culture that values stakeholder input but requires enhancement in collection methods, responsiveness, and utilization to achieve higher operational effectiveness and customer satisfaction.

The result of the study conforms with Ncentiva (2025) emphasized that collecting regular feedback from students, teachers, and parents allows school canteens to identify service gaps and align offerings with customer expectations.

The result is also supported by Fegade et al. (2019) highlighted that responding to stakeholder concerns and incorporating suggestions into operational practices improves service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty.

Bhattarai et al. (2024) noted that systematic feedback mechanisms, when effectively used, support informed decision-making and operational improvement in educational institutions.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to reward and incentive system;

Reward and Incentive System		
1. Canteen staff are given rewards or incentives based on performance.	5.00	Very Much Practice
2. Customers (students, staff) are rewarded for positive behavior or loyalty	4.86	Very Much Practice
3. Reward systems are documented and consistently	4.82	Very Much Practice

implemented.		
4. Utility personnel are given free snacks, lunch, and yearly incentives.	5.00	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.92	Very Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Reward and Incentive System in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.92, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen actively implements structured rewards and incentive programs to motivate staff, recognize positive behavior, and enhance operational performance. Specifically: 1. Canteen staff are given rewards or incentives based on performance received a mean of 5.00, reflecting the canteen's strong commitment to acknowledging outstanding performance and encouraging excellence among staff. 2. Customers and student staff are rewarded for positive behavior or loyalty scored 4.86, showing that the canteen promotes engagement and satisfaction through recognition of supportive behaviors. 3. Reward systems are documented and consistently implemented earned 4.82, indicating that the practices are formalized, transparent, and consistently applied to ensure fairness and motivation. 4. Utility personnel are given free snacks, lunch, and yearly incentives obtained 5.00, demonstrating comprehensive inclusion of all staff categories in the incentive programs, fostering morale and loyalty.

The overall grand mean of 4.92 signifies that reward and incentive practices are Very Much Practice, promoting a positive work environment, staff motivation, and customer engagement, which collectively contribute to sustained high-quality service and operational efficiency.

The result is supported by Brun and Dugas (2008) emphasized that structured reward and incentive programs significantly increase employee motivation, engagement, and performance in service-oriented institutions.

Ghosh et al. (2016) highlighted that rewards tied to performance and loyalty foster staff satisfaction and encourage consistent quality service delivery.

Fegade et al. (2019) noted that recognizing both employees and stakeholders strengthens morale, satisfaction, and overall operational effectiveness in school food services.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to recognition system;

Recognition System		
1. Outstanding canteen staff are recognized (monthly/quarterly/yearly)	4.90	Very Much Practice
2. Students or groups contributing to canteen improvement are acknowledged.	4.10	Much Practice
3. Top 3 most supportive employees in school canteen operations are recognized with certificates and gift certificates.	4.74	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.58	Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Recognition System in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is moderately observed, with a grand mean of 4.58, verbally interpreted as Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen implements recognition practices for staff and students, but there is room for improvement to consistently acknowledge all contributors and maximize motivation. Specifically: 1. Outstanding canteen staff are recognized monthly, quarterly, and yearly received a mean of 4.90, reflecting a strong practice of acknowledging staff performance and fostering a culture of excellence. 2. Students or groups contributing to canteen improvement are acknowledged scored 4.10, showing that recognition of student contributors is less frequent or systematic, suggesting an area for improvement to encourage more student engagement. 3. Top 3 most supportive employees in school canteen operations are recognized with certificates and gift certificates earned 4.74, indicating that recognition is applied to key supportive employees, reinforcing their contribution and motivation.

The overall grand mean of 4.58 demonstrates that recognition practices are Much Practice, signifying that while the canteen acknowledges outstanding performance, enhancing systematic recognition for all contributors could further improve morale, engagement, and sustained operational excellence.

The result of the study is supported by Brun and Dugas (2008) emphasized that employee recognition programs boost motivation, engagement, and overall job satisfaction, enhancing performance in service-oriented institutions.

More so, the study conforms to Fegade et al. (2019) noted that recognizing contributions from both staff and students strengthens morale and promotes active participation in institutional improvement initiatives.

Ghosh et al. (2016) highlighted that systematic acknowledgment, including certificates and tangible rewards, enhances employee loyalty and commitment to organizational goals.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to canteen gift certificates;

Canteen Gift Certificates		
1. Canteen gift certificates are distributed as part of reward/incentive system.	4.95	Very Much Practice
2. Gift certificates can be redeemed for food or items in the canteen.	4.92	Very Much Practice
3. Guidelines for issuance and use are clearly communicated.	4.84	Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.90	Very Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Canteen Gift Certificate system in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.90, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen effectively integrates gift certificates as part of its reward and incentive program, promoting motivation, loyalty, and engagement among staff and students. Specifically: 1. Canteen Gift Certificates are distributed as part of reward and incentive system received a mean of 4.95, reflecting consistent practice of using certificates to recognize and reward positive contributions. 2. Gift Certificates can be redeemed for food or items in the canteen scored 4.92, indicating that the certificates are practical, functional, and valued by recipients, reinforcing participation in reward programs. 3. Guidelines for issuance and use are clearly communicated earned 4.84, suggesting that while instructions are generally clear, further communication may enhance understanding and proper utilization.

The overall grand mean of 4.90 demonstrates that the use of gift certificates is Very Much Practice, supporting a positive and motivating environment, reinforcing reward systems, and promoting consistent engagement and satisfaction among stakeholders.

Brun and Dugas (2008) supported the result of the study where they emphasized that tangible recognition, such as gift certificates, strengthens motivation, engagement, and loyalty among employees.

The result aligns with the study of Fegade et al. (2019) noted that reward systems with redeemable incentives improve participation, satisfaction, and adherence to organizational goals.

Justine (2024) highlighted that integrating practical incentives into school cafeteria programs enhances operational efficiency and stakeholder morale.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to loyalty and discount cards;

Loyalty and Discount Cards		
1. A loyalty or discount card system is available to regular customers.	4.82	Very Much Practice
2. Cardholders are entitled to special promos or discounts.	4.84	Very Much Practice

3. The system is accessible and easy to use for students and staff.	4.71	Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.79	Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Loyalty and Discount Card system in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.79, verbally interpreted as Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen provides regular customers, including students and staff, with incentives that encourage repeat engagement, promote customer satisfaction, and enhance loyalty. Specifically: 1. A loyalty or discount card system is available to regular customers received a mean of 4.82, showing that the canteen has established a structured mechanism to reward consistent patronage. 2. Cardholders are entitled to special promos or discounts scored 4.84, reflecting that the benefits are meaningful and recognized by the stakeholders, encouraging continued participation. 3. The system is accessible and easy to use for students and staff earned 4.71, indicating that while the system is generally user-friendly, there may be slight room for improving accessibility or awareness among users.

The overall grand mean of 4.79 demonstrates that the loyalty and discount card practices are Much Practiced, contributing to stakeholder engagement, sustained patronage, and satisfaction, while also supporting the canteen's operational goals and financial sustainability.

The result conforms to Bhattarai et al. (2024) emphasized that loyalty programs in school canteens increase repeat engagement, customer satisfaction, and consistent revenue streams.

The study is aligned with Fegade et al. (2019) noted that discount and reward systems improve patronage behavior, motivate participation, and enhance overall service experience.

Furthermore, the result is supported by Justine (2024) highlighted that accessible and user-friendly loyalty systems in school food services contribute to operational efficiency and sustained stakeholder involvement.

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to satellite canteen system; and

Satellite Canteen System		
1. Satellite canteens follow the same standards as the main canteen.	4.95	Very Much Practice
2. There are satellite canteen stations to serve students in other areas.	4.90	Very Much Practice
3. Each grade level has a separate recess schedule to help manage crowding.	4.98	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.94	Very Much Practice

4.81-5.00 Very much practice; 3.81-4.80 Much practice; 2.81-3.80 Sometimes practice; 1.81-2.80 Less practice; 1.00-1.80 Not practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Satellite Canteen System in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.94, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. This indicates that the school effectively implements satellite canteen stations to ensure accessibility, reduce congestion, and maintain service quality across different areas of the campus. Specifically: 1. Satellite canteens follow the same standards as the main canteen received a mean of 4.95, reflecting consistent adherence to hygiene, operational, and service protocols, ensuring uniform quality across all stations. 2. Satellite canteen stations serve students in other areas scored 4.90, showing that the canteen expands its reach to provide convenience and accessibility to students in multiple locations. 3. Each grade level has a separate recess schedule to help manage crowding earned 4.98, indicating a highly organized system that minimizes congestion, promotes safety, and allows for smoother service flow.

The overall grand mean of 4.94 demonstrates that the Satellite Canteen System is Very Much Practice, contributing to operational efficiency, student convenience, and consistent service quality. This

system effectively supports crowd management and accessibility while maintaining the high standards of the main canteen.

The result is aligned with Beluan, et.al (2019) emphasized that satellite canteen stations improve accessibility, reduce crowding, and maintain uniform quality standards in educational institutions.

The result also conforms with the study of Bhattarai et al. (2024) noted that decentralizing food service through multiple stations enhances operational efficiency, student satisfaction, and adherence to service protocols.

More so, Justine (2024) highlighted that scheduling and organization of multiple service points in schools promote safety, convenience, and seamless food service delivery

On the extent of implementation of the school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and supporting income and operation with respect to Project Online Canteen Report System (OCRS)

Project OCRS (Online Canteen Reporting System)		
1. The canteen uses an online reporting system for operations and income.	4.84	Very Much Practice
2. OCRS can be accessed by the Principal and Canteen Manager to support informed financial decisions.	4.86	Very Much Practice
Grand Mean	4.85	Very Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Online Canteen Reporting System (OCRS) in Baras Pinugay Integrated High School Canteen is highly observed, with a grand mean of 4.85, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice. This indicates that the canteen effectively utilizes technology to monitor operations, track income, and provide real-time data for informed decision-making. Specifically: 1. The canteen uses an online canteen reporting system for operations and income received a mean of 4.84, reflecting that the system is consistently employed to streamline reporting, reduce errors, and maintain accurate financial records. 2. OCRS can be accessed by the principal and canteen manager to support informed financial decisions scored 4.86, showing that key stakeholders have timely access to operational data, enabling evidence-based management and strategic planning.

The overall grand mean of 4.85 demonstrates that the online reporting system is Very Much Practice, supporting transparency, accountability, and efficient management of the canteen's operations and finances. Such systems enhance operational efficiency, reduce manual reporting errors, and provide stakeholders with actionable insights.

The result is supported by Bhattarai et al. (2024) emphasized that digital reporting systems improve transparency, accuracy, and decision-making efficiency in institutional food service management.

Justine (2024) highlighted that online operational and financial tracking in school canteens facilitates informed managerial decisions and enhances accountability. Fegade et al. (2019) note that technology-driven reporting systems streamline operations, reduce manual errors, and promote effective resource management in educational institutions.

**COMPOSITE TABLE ON THE SCHOOL CANTEEN
BEST PRACTICES AND INNOVATIONS**

School Canteen Best Practices and Innovations	Grand Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Compliance to Food Safety standards	4.92	Very Much Practice
Daily operations and Financial Management	4.89	Very Much Practice
7S Embedded canteen	4.86	Very Much Practice
Data-based inventory system	4.92	Very Much Practice
Voice of the customer (VOC)-based system	4.63	Much Practice
Reward and incentive system	4.92	Very Much Practice
Recognition system	4.58	Much Practice
Canteen gift certificates	4.90	Very Much Practice
Loyalty and discount cards	4.79	Much Practice
Satellite canteen system	4.94	Very Much Practice
Project OCRS (Online Canteen Report System)	4.85	Very Much Practice
Overall Mean	4.84	Very Much Practice

It can be gleaned from the table that the Satellite Canteen System, with a grand mean of 4.94 and verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice, ranks 1st. This is followed by the Database Inventory System and the Reward and Incentive System, both with a grand mean of 4.92, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice, and ranking 3rd. Meanwhile, the least practice canteen best practice and innovation is the Recognition System, with a grand mean of 4.58 and verbally interpreted as Much Practice, followed by the Voice of the Customer (VOC)-Based System, which ranks 2nd to the last with a grand mean of 4.63, also verbally interpreted as Much Practice.

The overall mean of 4.84, verbally interpreted as Very Much Practice, indicates that Baras Pinugay Integrated High School has successfully institutionalized highly effective and sustainable canteen practices and innovations. These results suggest that the canteen not only maintains high standards in food safety, operational efficiency, employee motivation, and customer service but also effectively integrates digital reporting and inventory systems to enhance transparency and management.

The result of the study aligns with Beluan, et.al. (2019) and Nicodemus & Versano (2022) on the Satellite Canteen System, who reported that distributing service points in school cafeterias improves accessibility, reduces congestion, and maintains consistent service quality.

The use of inventory management systems supports findings by Justine (2024) and Bhattarai et al. (2024), showing that digital or structured inventory systems improve accuracy, reduce waste, and enhance operational efficiency.

The implementation of incentives is consistent with Ghosh et al. (2016) and Brun & Dugas (2008), emphasizing that reward systems motivate staff, increase engagement, and improve service quality.

While slightly lower, the practice of recognition is supported by Uslu et al. (2025) and Thorndike

et al. (2014), showing that acknowledging contributions improves employee morale and performance.

Customer feedback practices are supported by Ncentiva (2025) and Fegade et al. (2019), which highlight the importance of feedback systems in improving service quality and stakeholder satisfaction.

2. What are the comments and suggestions of students, teachers, and parents to further improve canteen services?

Based on the results, the following comments and suggestions were highlighted: Parents and Teachers recommended strengthening the Voice of the Customer (VOC) mechanism by providing a Canteen Suggestion Box where they can write their feedback, comments, and inquiries regarding canteen services. This will ensure that the concerns and recommendations of stakeholders are continuously gathered and addressed. Parents raised concerns regarding scheduling of recess per grade level to avoid overcrowding, congestion, and long queues in the canteen. They suggested that a staggered recess schedule be implemented per grade level, particularly in the satellite canteen system, to promote orderliness and ensure the safety and comfort of learners. Teachers further emphasized that canteen staff and food handlers should undergo regular training on food safety and hygiene, particularly on proper food handling, preparation, and storage, to prevent food contamination and safeguard the health of students. Students suggested that they should be properly oriented and informed about the innovations introduced by the canteen, such as the use of Canteen Gift Certificates and Loyalty or Discount Cards, including clear guidelines on how they can avail and benefit from these initiatives when purchasing food items. Students also proposed the establishment of a Recognition Program that acknowledges individual students or grade levels as the “Most Supportive Patrons of the School Canteen.” This initiative aims to foster a sense of involvement and appreciation among learners while promoting sustained support for the canteen operations

3. What is the comparative analysis of the canteen’s net sales during School Year 2023–2024 and School Year 2024–2025 with the implementation of best practices and innovations?

The comparative analysis of the canteen’s net sales before and after the implementation of best practices and innovations reveals a remarkable improvement in its financial performance. For School Year 2023–2024, the recorded net income was ₱249,232.80, while in School Year 2024–2025, after introducing canteen best practices and innovative strategies, the net income significantly increased to ₱463,238.00. This represents a substantial 85.86% growth in net sales.

The data suggest that the implementation of innovative practices such as the introduction of loyalty and discount cards, canteen gift certificates, improved food handling standards, and enhanced customer feedback mechanisms, contributed greatly to higher patronage and sales. Furthermore, the increase in the average net income per pupil from 0.9 to 1.75 underscores the effectiveness of these best practices and innovations in encouraging more frequent and supportive canteen use among students. Overall, the results emphasized that systematic improvement in management, service quality, and customer engagement strategies directly translated into increased profitability and sustainability of the school canteen operations.

4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed to further strengthen, sustain, and institutionalize the implementation of school canteen best practices and innovations in delivering quality service and sustaining income and operations?

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ACTION PLAN

Strengthening, Sustaining, and Institutionalizing School Canteen Best Practices and Innovations of Baras Pinugay Integrated High School

I. RATIONALE

Based on the findings of the study, the school canteen practices and innovations are very much practiced and implemented. Thus, this action plan focuses on sustaining, strengthening, and institutionalizing these practices to ensure continuous quality service, financial sustainability, and operational efficiency.

II. GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To sustain and institutionalize the implementation of school canteen best practices and innovations ensuring quality service delivery, efficient operations, financial sustainability, and stakeholder satisfaction.

III. ACTION PLAN MATRIX

Key Area	Objective	Key Strategies / Activities	Persons Involved	Resources Needed	Timeline	Success Indicators
1. Institutionalization of Food Safety and Quality Standards	Ensure continuous compliance with DepEd food safety policies	Regular food safety training; integration of food safety in SOP manual; quarterly compliance audit; strict hygiene monitoring	School Head, Canteen Manager, Canteen staff, Health Coordinator	DepEd orders, manuals, sanitation supplies	Quarterly / Ongoing	Sustained zero case of food poisoning; no related complaint; consistent hygiene compliance
2. Standardization of Service Quality Delivery System	Maintain high-level, consistent, and efficient service delivery	Develop Service Quality Manual; enforce service time standards; regular staff retraining; queue and flow system maintenance	Canteen Manager, Staff, School Admin	SOP manual, training materials	Continuous	Reduced waiting time; consistent customer satisfaction
3. Strengthening Financial Sustainability and Transparency	Ensure long-term financial stability and accountability	Institutionalize digital or manual accounting system; quarterly financial audit;	School Canteen Checking and Auditing Committee, Canteen manager	Accounting tools, audit templates	Daily/Monthly/Year-end	Stable income flow; transparent records

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		benchmarking of income performance				
4. Sustainability of 7S and Operational Efficiency System	Maintain organized and efficient workplace environment	Monthly 7S audit; reward compliance system; integration into staff evaluation	Monitoring Team, Canteen Staff	7S checklist	Monthly	Consistent clean and organized canteen
5. Institutionalization of Data-Based Inventory System	Ensure continuous availability of stocks and minimize wastage	Digital inventory system adoption; standardized procurement plan;	Canteen Manager Canteen Staff	Inventory software/logbook	Weekly Continuous	Zero stock-outs; reduced wastage
6. Continuous Voice of Customer (VOC) Integration	Sustain customer-centered service improvement	Institutionalize feedback system; quarterly satisfaction analysis; action tracking system	Canteen Manager Canteen Committee School Admin	Feedback tools, survey forms	Monthly / Quarterly	Improved clientele satisfaction ratings
7. Strengthening Staff Development, Incentives, and Professionalism	Sustain high staff performance and motivation	Annual capability training; institutional reward system; performance-based evaluation	Canteen Mager School Admin, HR Committee	Training funds, evaluation tools	Quarterly / Annual	Improved staff efficiency and behavior
8. Maintenance of Loyalty and Customer Engagement Systems	Sustain customer retention and satisfaction	Continuous loyalty program; promotional strategies; review of pricing and discounts	Canteen Manager	Loyalty cards, promo materials	Ongoing	Increased repeat customers
9. Institutionalization of Satellite Canteen System	Maintain accessibility and service efficiency	Formal guidelines for satellite stations; regular monitoring; standardized service procedures	Canteen manager Canteen staff Utility personnel School Head	Service setup materials	Daily operation Canteen	Reduced congestion; faster service flow
10. Full Integration of Online Canteen Reporting System (OCRS)	Sustain digital monitoring and transparency	Full adoption of OCRS; integration into school reporting system	ICT Coordinator, Canteen Manager School Head	ICT tools, internet access	Continuous	Real-time reporting; improved decision-making

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IV. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

To ensure the effective implementation, sustainability, and continuous improvement of the school canteen best practices and innovations, a systematic Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) framework shall be conducted. This will serve as a mechanism for assessing performance, identifying gaps, and providing evidence-based inputs for decision-making and improvement.

1. Quarterly Program Review

A quarterly review shall be conducted to assess the overall implementation of the action plan. This will include the evaluation of food safety compliance, service quality delivery, financial performance, inventory management, and customer satisfaction. The school administration, canteen committee, and relevant stakeholders shall participate in the review to ensure transparency and accountability.

2. Customer Satisfaction Survey

Regular customer satisfaction surveys shall be administered among students, teachers, and parents to gather feedback on food quality, service efficiency, pricing, cleanliness, and overall canteen experience. Results shall be analyzed to identify strengths and areas for improvement, which will serve as the basis for service enhancement strategies.

3. Financial Monitoring and Audit

Periodic financial audits shall be conducted on a monthly basis to ensure transparency, accuracy, and accountability in canteen income and expenditures. This includes the review of daily sales records, procurement expenses, profit margins, and fund utilization. Findings shall be reported to the school head and finance committee for proper action.

4. Operational Benchmarking

The canteen's performance shall be benchmarked annually or semi-annually based on key indicators such as net income, service time efficiency, inventory wastage rate, compliance level, and customer satisfaction ratings. This will allow comparison with previous school years and identification of performance improvements resulting from implemented innovations.

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5. Feedback and Action Tracking System

All feedback collected from stakeholders, including complaints, suggestions, and recommendations, shall be systematically recorded, analyzed, and acted upon. An action tracking system shall be established to ensure that all concerns are addressed in a timely and documented manner.

6. Documentation and Reporting

All monitoring activities, findings, and evaluation results shall be properly documented and submitted to the school administration. This will serve as basis for policy refinement, future planning, and institutionalization of best practices.

V. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

The implementation of this comprehensive action plan is expected to yield the following significant and sustainable outcomes:

1. Improved Service Quality Delivery

The canteen will consistently provide fast, efficient, and customer-centered services, resulting in reduced waiting time, improved food handling practices, and enhanced overall customer experience.

2. Sustained Financial Stability and Transparency

Through strengthened financial management systems and regular audits, the canteen is expected to achieve stable income generation, reduced financial discrepancies, and improved transparency and accountability in all financial transactions.

3. Institutionalization of Best Practices and Innovations

All effective practices such as food safety compliance, 7S system, VOC system, inventory management, and OCRS will be fully institutionalized as standard operating procedures, ensuring continuity even with personnel changes.

4. Enhanced Customer Satisfaction and Engagement

Students, teachers, and parents will experience improved canteen services, leading to higher satisfaction levels, stronger trust in canteen operations, and increased customer loyalty.

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5. Efficient and Organized Canteen Operations

The integration of systematic operational procedures, data-based inventory systems, and structured workflow processes will result in reduced wastage, improved efficiency, and smoother daily operations.

6. Sustainable and Innovative School Canteen System

The school canteen will evolve into a model of a sustainable, innovative, and well-managed support system that contributes not only to student welfare but also to school development programs through generated income.

PREPARED BY:

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 HEAD TEACHER I

"Bridging Gaps and Building Trust Through Empathetic and Student-centered Teaching"

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Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the school canteen of Baras Pinugay Integrated High School has successfully implemented various best practices and innovations that significantly contribute to quality service delivery and sustainable financial operations. Among the areas assessed, the following were found to be "Very Much Practice" were Satellite canteen system, Compliance to food safety standards, daily operations and financial management, 7S-embedded canteen, data-based inventory system, reward and incentive system, canteen gift certificates, loyalty and discount cards, and online canteen report system. However, areas such as VOC-based feedback mechanisms and recognition system were observed to be practiced to a lesser extent and could benefit from further development.

The suggestions and comments of the students, teachers, and parents were to intensify the VOC-based system, to establish a schedule for recess per grade level to reduce overcrowding in satellite canteen, and to orient them with the recognition system, utilization of canteen gift certificates and loyalty and discount cards, and to conduct regular training on food handling and safety practices among food handlers.

Comparative analysis of net sales between School Years 2023–2024 and 2024–2025 also showed a marked improvement in financial performance, suggesting a strong correlation between best practices, innovation implementation and income sustainability.

Based on the proposed action plan, it was concluded that sustaining and institutionalizing these best practices and innovation is essential to ensure long-term improvement in school canteen management and operation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to further strengthen the best practices and innovations in the Baras Pinugay Integrated High School (BPIHS) canteen. These aim to improve service quality, ensure efficient operations, and sustain financial growth.

1. Continuous Monitoring and Compliance

The school should continuously monitor and ensure strict compliance with DepEd Orders and food safety standards to maintain quality service and safe food handling.

2. Regular Evaluation of Innovations

The school should regularly assess the effectiveness of the implemented best practices and innovations to determine their impact and identify areas for improvement.

3. Capacity Building for Canteen Staff

Regular training should be conducted for canteen personnel focusing on food safety, hygiene, proper food handling, and customer service to ensure high-quality service delivery.

4. Strengthen Feedback Mechanisms

The use of customer satisfaction surveys and a suggestion box should be strengthened to continuously gather feedback from students, teachers, and parents for service improvement.

5. Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)

The proposed Monitoring and Evaluation system in the action plan should be fully implemented, including quarterly reviews, financial audits, benchmarking, and feedback tracking to ensure sustained improvement.

6. Sustain and Institutionalize the Action Plan

The proposed action plan should be adopted as a long-term guide in managing the canteen to ensure that best practices, innovations, and systems are consistently implemented and improved.

7. Further Studies

Future research may be conducted with a wider scope, additional variables, or different settings to further validate and improve the effectiveness of the best practices and innovations.

8. Benchmarking and Adoption by Other Schools

The study may serve as a model for other school canteens. Its best practices and innovations may be benchmarked and adapted to help improve service quality, income generation, and operational efficiency in other schools.

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